

Work is Worship- A Need to Ponder

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Abstract

'Work is worship', is an illustrious proverb. When working came into inception the very first philosophy treated it as something to be done religiously. The piousness and allegiance were the traits, why were? Because in due course of time the sanctity of mind and spirit towards work was dissolved and materialism weighed heavier. The belonging of workplace is not the pace of the day rather it is, how to keep oneself detached with organization focusing only on making money. Spirituality is inside integrity of a person which works for the wellbeing of all without causing any harm to anybody and then to work for the upliftment of all at personal and professional level.

We have to ponder that what are the reasons behind this change in approach? Is it good for organization and employee or not? If it is harmful then what are the area in which it has to be curtailed? In spite of number of spiritual Gurus and reforming centers why the animal instincts of human beings are still increasing multi dimensionally. The paper will be focusing on the reasons of lack of spirituality and some suggestions as well.

The chirping of birds in the morning is a scene rare to be found in concrete metropolitans, and not only there but in villages too. Urbanization stole from us the natural beauty and on the same footage materialism has stolen the piousness of inner self.

In this rat race there are many challenges that society is facing in political, social, economic, administrative, ethical arenas. But a slight ponder makes it clear that the actual or the root confront is the challenge of self bankrupt i.e. people have no control over their emotions rather they don't wish to have any rule book for their own self.

Everything appears to be a matter of profit only, be it in form of some material benefit, or it comes some other way. Such hue and cry these days over various social issues is the result of lack of spirituality at workplace. There was a time when work was considered as worship and it was done religiously with full honesty, but today in majority it is done for the sake of doing it. Observance from a minor to a major level gives the same result. From a labour to the key position holders all are busy in securing their job that too by hook or crook. People know that if they won't be compromising with their boss they may lose the job as the queue outside the office is quiet long. The one whose job is secure takes it as an advantage that he needs not to worry about job security whether he puts up the labour required for the job or not, so he gives up working and enjoy the privileges given. It could be said that one reason behind this casual approach is the constraints of private job and benefits of public one.

Secondly there is stress that penetrated to our nerves in last two decades; it is the stress to earn more, to prove oneself, to have financial and social status, to be at the top, to maintain shattered relationships. In order to fulfill these we compromised with our work

and deliberately stopped piousness to it, as many other tasks appear to be of much importance.

This approach gives rise to a self centric personality, and selfishness can never be spiritual. Our motto should be that what we have taken from world, culture and society we have to return that back, but the fate is that this sensitivity is missing.

A teacher is interested only in completion of course, doctor diagnose two additional diseases with the actual one, advocates brawl for the party which could pay better, files kept on pending for years in govt. departments, religious and spiritual leaders, only sermonize instead of putting up a live example of their own, media is busy in sensation, and political leaders to lure the voters, students are busy with brands and models and parents in giving them money in place of time.

In fine it could be said that from politicians to administrators, judiciary to social workers, business men to service class, literary laureates to scientists, classes to masses, the direct or indirect work is done only for the sake of work, not perceived with the intention of organizational welfare resulting in development of society. In this scenario it is funny to expect from people to think workplace religiously theirs'. Spirituality is so much in air these days but not to follow rather to use it as a status symbol (refined religious approach of vision.)

By this time a natural question is likely to come to the mind of readers why such an importance is given to the word 'spirituality' at workplace. The reason is that spirituality affects an organizational performance positively. It is expected to moderate the relationship between negative perceptions of the organization and organizational cynicism. In organizations which try to improve the spiritual development of their members, creativity increase, team performance satisfaction and organizational commitment have been reported.¹ It is believed that encouraging spirituality in the workplace would be advantageous for the organization. Popularity of spirituality in workplace is a tool that guarantees the survival of the organizations against current uncertain environment, not only this but it guarantees personal up gradation of an individual in person as well as in professional. If the individual is having a strong sense of spirituality, cynicism may be reduced, as the person feels an internal sense of purpose surrounding his/her life, and believes that there is higher meaning for the events that occur in all the aspects of life.²

Now the burning issue is that if it is of that much importance why it is complicated to practice it? There might be many reasons like personal stress, to accomplish certain targets and goals. In order to maintain social and financial status to stab the one or to take erroneous measures come out to be a short way to success. Then with privatization and some technical loopholes in administration there observed insecurity among people, this fear of survival stops them to be ethical if it comes to their job. Then again as a fault of system many non deserving people enjoy the benefits given by govt. And the deserving ones left out with no option to make their ends meet by hook or crook. Last but not the least reason is that today classes provide the mechanic and calculative lessons to earn bread instead of providing an amalgamation in proper ratio of both ethics and knowledge.

These rationale emerge as a threat to the credibility of any organization, as a result of the mentioned reasons, there appears lack of enthusiasm among employees, non performance, enhancement of materialism approach, increase in inside organization corruption, increase in personal weaknesses of the employees which again is harmful for any organization.

Contrary to it, Spiritual perception not only improves efficiency, but more importantly reaches a relaxation and inner satisfaction along with a long happiness and provides a cordial environment among co workers which ultimately led to success of organization and employee as well. A spiritual organization in addition to employees' satisfaction raise, improve honesty, confidence, respect, responsibility, and personal stability in the workplace.³ Spirituality tends to increase the belonging of an employee to his / her workplace.

Employee morale has a direct influence on productivity, which is why organizations spend large sums of money trying to make working environments comfortable, pleasant, and even luxurious. When sincerity and pure motives are combined with highly developed business leadership and consistent decision making skills, the outcome is a powerful and highly motivated organization. In searching for business solutions, one must be innovative in developing ways to positively impact not only the client but also co-workers and peers. "Spirituality in the Workplace" is more than just a concept; it is a practical method for attaining business success.⁴

One spiritual commentator describes prayers and mediation as remedies for clearing the clogged arteries of our soul. Because individual needs differ, just as our appetite for food and its consumption varies, everybody responds in a different manner. At the end of the day, we are all human beings with hearts and souls. Everyone has different lives and different issues; however the one thing that unites us – especially in the workplace—is that we are all trying to do our best and to have our work appreciated, for the benefit of making the world a better place to live. Contentment in the workplace, bred by a sense of spiritual fulfilment, is every bit a valuable commodity. Our attitudes and entitlement take on a different shape only when we are on the receiving end of the treatment we wish all would aspire to.⁵

"The way 'spirituality' is often used suggests that we exist solely as a collection of individuals, not as members of a religious community, and that religious life is merely a private journey."⁶ Although religion affects individual's spirituality and plays an important role in governing our day to day behaviour at work through ritual practices but the religion should not be interpreted in terms of spirituality, because spirituality is personal; religion is social.⁷

Characteristics of a Spiritual Workplace: Suggestions as Well

Regardless of this ongoing debate, identifying desired characteristics of spiritual workplaces can bring us closer to understanding the role that spirituality can play in organizations, the way it can function to positively impact the bottom line, and the value it might bring to members of the work community.

Spirituality may be thought as an incompatible with modern trends of the day, but still deep somewhere it can provide insight to the mankind and organizations. The mentioned six effects⁸ can be associated with a model of workplace spirituality. It Emphasizes Sustainability, Values Contribution, Prizes Creativity, Cultivates Inclusion, Develops Principles, Promotes Vocation

A systemic view of work and contribution in the world promotes links between sustainability and an awareness of limited resources. This approach to design, production, and commerce is being increasingly associated with spirituality because it seeks to contribute to the greater good in the world. An understanding of sustainable growth and development includes a well-thought-out strategy that identifies potential long-term impacts or implications of actions. Not only in one field or the other but wherever pious goals are there sustainability comes.

More than providing excellent service for customers, global service indicates a larger sense of responsibility to contribute to the betterment of the world. While the local family business may not provide products and services that will improve the quality of life in third world countries, some companies historically have fundamentally understood that they have to make the world a better place through the products or services that they sell. Today's spiritual organization is deliberate in implementing a vision that is built around contributions to the betterment of mankind. It promotes work outside of the organization that contributes to and "gives back" to society through community and volunteer service. Spiritually aware managers and businesses consider themselves servants of employees, customers, and the community.

Creativity is a necessary part of the development cycle, it is the key to successfully navigating changes. The artistic industries have long recognized the spiritual nature of individual and group creative processes, and many educators understand the importance of seamless, daily incorporation of creativity in helping their students learn. A spiritual workplace provides resources to help people to uncover their creative potential and to practice creativity within the organization.

The spiritual organization respects and values individuals' life experiences and the lessons learned from them. Such an organization is intentional in its efforts to include individuals who bring appropriate skill sets to a particular job, but who may have been excluded historically from participating in a professional community of practice due to circumstances they did not choose. Such historic exclusion from the workplace has included people with physical disabilities, people whose skin colour or ethnic origin differs from those of the majority population, and those who have been discriminated against due to gender or sexual orientation. Increasingly, corporations are seeing the value of their employees working together in community toward a commonly held vision. They have a sense that the concepts of love and acceptance within a cultural context of care builds a sense of community that supports the work of the company and that has a direct impact on the bottom line.

Organizations have to realize the benefits of treating the people by actively supporting the formulation of ethical principles that promote personal growth, long-term character

development, and personal connections of faith and work development. Assisting employees in integrating personal growth, learning, and faith with job performance benefits the organization. This type of principled emphasis includes providing resources that help employees to understand themselves better, develop successful professional and personal relationships, and enhance personal management skills. Employees need to be encouraged to develop an accurate and realistic sense of the impact that other people have on them and the impact that they have on others.

Organizations have to be aware of the benefits of shared ownership of corporate values by every member of the organization. By acknowledging that one's general search for spiritual growth and fulfilment need not be separate from one's work, organizations lay the groundwork for spiritual development to assist in engendering understanding among employees. Companies that understand workplace spirituality go beyond being supportive of learning and development by helping employees develop a sense of "calling" or identification of passion about their lives and their work. Companies required emphasizing the discovery and appropriate utilization of individual's calibre and encouraging employees to use their unique skills within the organization. Grounded religious faith development is recognized as an important and deeply personal part of growth for many people, one that can help them more easily recognize their vocations.

The six components presented here as building blocks toward considering a model of workplace spirituality serve as a partial framework for engaging in a broader conversation of spirituality's place and influence in culture. The recent trend is to recognize the spiritual nature of people and the importance of incorporating the "whole person" at work.

Certain virtues such as courage, honesty, fairness and empathy are considered as traits necessary for ethical behaviour⁹; Emotions organize intellectual capacities and indeed create the sense of self.¹⁰ Spirituality foster these traits and emotions resulting in preparation of a serene and cordial atmosphere at workplace.

Spirituality in this new sense is a private activity, although it may be pursued with a group of the like-minded, it is not 'institutional' in that it does not involve membership in a group that has claims on its members.

Spirituality is the state of intimate relationship with the inner self of higher values and morality as well as recognizing the truth of inner nature of people. The concept of spirituality at work place can be explained as an experience of interconnectedness, shared by all those involved in the work process, initially triggered by the awareness that each is individually driven by an inner power, which raises and maintains his/her sense of honesty, kindness and courage, consequently leading to the collective creation of an aesthetically motivational environment characterised by a sense of purpose, high ethical standards, acceptance, peace, trust, thus establishing an atmosphere of enhanced team performance and overall harmony.¹¹

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